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Research Article

EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT AND MANAGEMENT¹Ryeesa Patres, ²Ms. Sana Sehar, ³Muhammad Afzal, ⁴Dr. Syed Amir Gilani¹Student. The University of Lahore, ²Assistant professor. . The University of Lahore, ³associate professor. The University of Lahore, ⁴Dean faculty of allied health sciences. The University of Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

Employee engagement is ahead a massive and perilous reputation in today's extremely modest and energetic business environment. Engaged personnel is a vigorous strength for the organization that donates their energies for the profit of organization. It categorizes the variances in engagement level of staffs in work and administration.

Objectives: *The aim of this is to recognize the elementary concept of employee engagement and to study the different measurements of employee engagement with the references of multiple literatures.*

Results: *The study similarly enhances the limited literature on employee engagement part that has observed enormous disorder in the procedure of attainments, unions and rationalizing in previous few years.*

Conclusion: *The conclusion is the significances of the study defined directly above normal level of determination in engagement among the workers. The study equally improves the limited literature on employee engagement portion that has detected enormous complaint in the method of achievements, unions and rationalizing in previous few years.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Now a days, each organization seeks to have a puddle of engaged workers. Employee engagement has been associated for the construction of a strong organization. Staff engagement, can make or destroy the business lowermost line (Lockwood, 2015). Engaging workers particularly by providing them involvement, independence, and trust is the greatest wide-ranging support for the employees. What workers expect and what organization provides is a compound and critical problem to be talked by recognizing such a gap. Engaged workers are actually, cognitively, and passionately committed to their association and extremely involved in their duties with a countless interest. They have a habit of going a spare mile out there the employment promised contract (Shukla, Adhikari, & Singh, 2015).

Hence, organizations effort to hire, preserve and keep in mind those workers who are high in their dynamism, ambitious to donate, devotion, assurance and engagement stages. Employee engagement has a straight influence on the worker's association and efficiency and further on the presentation of the complete association. An entirely engaged worker is supplementary well-organized, transports advanced points of client gratification, achieves complex yield levels, and confirms inferior business rates, which all interpreted into better general performance (Buhler, 2015).

Case Scenario:

Step	Problem Solving	Stage	Decision Making
1	Identify the problem	1	Frame the decision
2	Explore alternatives	2	Innovate to address needs and identify alternatives
3	Select an alternative	3	Decide and commit to act
4	Implement the solution	4	Manage consequences
5	Evaluate the situation	4 & 1	Manage consequences and frame the related decisions

Theoretical framework:

This is supported by McGregor's declaration that managers' problem solving and decision-making

It was the start of the month; the duty roster had been declared with the duties of all staff nurses along with different departments. My duty also changed from one department to another. On 3rd of September, I was on duty. My one colleague whose duty also had been changed, wanted to avail leave for her brother's marriage. While on the other hand, a second staff who was performing duty in that department also wanted to avail leave for some purpose. The manager of that department provided the leave to second staff but did not compromise with the new staff. It all situation left a very bad impression on the new staff and she becomes very non corporative after that time. She never gave her good performance and a developed output. She becomes very hard about any kind of co-operate with the sister and all other staff.

Management Process:

After all this scenario, I analyzed that good benefits and sustainability are very important for the efficient performance of a worker. If personnel are not provided with better profits, they have no insight to give their excellence for any purpose. I observed, that the manager of that department has not a good decision-making power. The manager has not the capability to understand the problem of the staff and just showed favoritism between the old and the new one worker. I applied the problem solving and decision-making theory to settle down the condition and provide the employee satisfaction for a better outcome.

theory are closely related to employee engagement. Problem solving theory suggested that directors distinguish destructive or constructive influences on

the power of the worker while in decision making theory, managers observe an optimistic significance of imploring worker contribution on their managerial authority and structural effectiveness.

RESULTS:

After applying the theory, the satisfaction of the staff is observed and the quality of the work and a developed outcome is perceived. Employee engagement have established several ideas to clarify employee actions, performances, and spiritual conditions. Employee engagement mention a relationship of person's participation and gratification in addition to passion for exertion. Work engagement is demarcated as "an optimistic, rewarding, work-related state of awareness that is categorized by potency, enthusiasm, and interest". Even though these associated terms have slightly dissimilar meanings to one another.

DISCUSSION:

As the objective of the study is to evaluate the modifications in the engagement level of workers on the foundation of job appearances. These outcomes are alike with conclusions of approximately of the earlier studies where no relation was detected among gender and work engagement (Chaudhary & Rangnekar, 2017).

Businesses are resisting for cumulative their concert, market stake, good benefit and sustainability of business in a cut-throat opposition instant, and administrators have been struggling with frequent tasks of revenue, low production, conflicts, and low incentive of their workers. Nowadays, in order to prosper and put their business in advance of participants the necessity for extremely engaged staffs develop the crucial factors for the employers. Organizations are accentuating upon the consequence of employee engagement though pleasing into attention of all the positive results that joined employees could carry the workplace towards developed output, client fulfilment, revolution and abundant more (Towers Perrin's Global Workforce Study, 2016).

Employees from changed socio-demographic contextual will have dissimilar requirements, outlooks, projections and significances. The organization should evaluate employee separately in relation to their varied contextual as there is no solitary thumb rule to provide their unlike necessities. These rising worker dynamics impose the prospects of personnel from changed sections of the corporations in order to participate, and judge what companies are organized to suggest for the employees in diverse stages of supply (Balain and

Sparrow, 2017).

With the appreciation of employee engagement as a important component for structural achievement, each organization efforts to produce, grow and keep advantageous organizational setting where employees lean towards to present their very greatest work in the business, sustain appointment to their exertion laterally with the business progression and lastly donates to the general accomplishment of the organization. Although trying to achieve such designation through vast investment of incomes (Sharma & Garg, 2017).

The knowledge and stages of engagement at workplace can differ from individuals due to diverse demographic, occupation and organizational appearances. Such person alterations mean to classify the social indications from the working situation and seal in the gaps in the past studies (Sharma & Singh, 2018).

CONCLUSION:

To complete, the consequences of the study outlined directly above normal level of effort in engagement between the workers. The results of the study represent important changes in the work engagement level of staffs with dissimilar job features, such as employee position in the administrative grading. The credible policies anticipated to donate towards classifying new instructions in the area of workers engagement by distinguishing the value of employee engagement. The study similarly enhances the limited literature on employee engagement part that has observed enormous disorder in the procedure of attainments, unions and rationalizing in previous few years.

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